

Data Access Mechanism to Allow Multiple Level Permissions in Energy Management Solutions Supported by IoT devices

Nuno Teixeira

Research Group on Intelligent
Engineering and Computing for
Advanced Innovation and Development
Polytechnic of Porto (ISEP/IPP)
Porto, Portugal
nudal@isep.ipp.pt

Luis Gomes

Research Group on Intelligent
Engineering and Computing for
Advanced Innovation and Development
Polytechnic of Porto (ISEP/IPP)
Porto, Portugal
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8597-3383>

Zita Vale

Polytechnic of Porto (ISEP/IPP)
Porto, Portugal
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4560-9544>

Abstract— The use of energy management systems allows the management of electrical loads and resources inside a building. The variety of models allows end-users to optimize their energy usage considering multiple constraints while considering the end-users context and preferences. However, the sharing of data among users and entities, especially external entities, such as microgrid operators, energy community operators, and aggregators is an issue that needs to be addressed to protect data privacy. The proposed solution solves this issue by using signed tokens while being compliant with the European General Data Protection Regulation. The proposed solution is presented in this paper and demonstrated using real data regarding an office building. The results demonstrated the potential of this solution and the possibility of its use to protect the ownership rights of data, given the power to the owner and allow them to define the permissions of each data.

Keywords— Data access, Energy management systems, IoT devices, JavaScript object notation web tokens,

I. INTRODUCTION

The use of energy management systems (EMS) is common in smart grids, enabling the management of electrical loads and resources using centralized or decentralized approaches [1]. This type of system has been deployed in end-users and is presented in smart homes, enabling the efficient control of resources while considering the context [2]. EMS also opens the possibility of including artificial intelligence (AI) models, namely learning models that are able to learn from users and context and provide an intelligence control [3].

EMS also enables the active participation of end-users in the smart grid. Because end-users are able to control their energy usage, demand-side management is possible, and active participation can be achieved. For instance, end-users can participate in demand response programs [4] and in energy transactions [5]. However, these participations demand the sharing of end-user data, demanding end-users to accept the sharing of data.

Inside the facility, EMS can be supported by the internet of things (IoT) devices, enabling a feasible solution for remote monitoring and control [6]. A significant set of IoT devices have been used in and proposed/created for EMS [7][8]. In EMS, IoT devices can be seen as enablers of the EMS technology, as they provide the means to implement energy-related models [9].

Although practical, the massive use of IoT devices together with the sharing of data required by the active participation of end-users, raise issues regarding data privacy and data access rights [10]. In 2016, the European Parliament and the European Council regulated the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data with the directive 95/46/EC regarding the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [11]. Therefore, EMS must address the issues of data, especially because the data is owned by the user and is classified as private.

This paper proposes a data access mechanism for EMS that allows multiple level permissions according to the data owner settings. The solution is based on JavaScript object notation web tokens (JWT) to identify the entity that requested the data and to assure that each entity only has access to the data it needs and that was granted by the data owner. To test the proposed solution, it was used real data in a co-working environment where multiple entities, with different permission levels, request the building's data.

After this first introductory section, it will be presented, in section II, some of the related works regarding the use of IoT in EMS. Section III will detail the proposed solution, including architecture, how IoT devices are integrated, the data access tool, and the RESTful API. The case study, and its results, will be presented in section IV, and section V will have the main conclusions of this work.

II. RELATED WORKS

The first known IoT device was developed in 1982 to monitor a Coke Machine at the Carnegie Mellon University in Pittsburgh [12]. The concept of IoT can be seen as an ecosystem where all devices, such as smart machines or any type of object, are all connected [13]. Our smartphones can be seen as IoT devices integrating several sensors. It is expected that in 2022 there will be at least one IoT device installed in 216.9 million homes worldwide [14].

The monitoring and control functionalities over electrical loads and resources enable the use of IoT devices in energy management systems. The use of IoT devices is important, and a commonly used device used in energy management systems is the smart plug. For instance, in the solution proposed by Heo et al. [15], smart plugs are used for a centralized energy management system. However, the IoT devices available on the market have the problem regarding

their integration with third-party software. Some are closed systems and others give very little information on how to be used by third parties. Trying to solve this issue, some frameworks for IoT integration was been proposed, such as the one proposed by Barbierato et al. [16] enabling software in the loop real-time simulation, with built-in system controllers or smart meters, and the one proposed by Terroso-Saenz et al. [17] that is a platform capable of analysing energy data from heterogeneous IoT devices.

Luis Gomes et al. [18] proposed an EMS supported by IoT devices that were able to be deployed in a single-board computer. This solution allows the management of end-users facilities as well as their representation in a microgrid and smart grid. The IoT devices allow the management of energy [19], and enabled the transaction of energy among end-users [20]. In this solution, IoT devices were integrated using energy resources classes that allowed the use of HTTP (REST API), Modbus/TCP, and Modbus/RTU. The system was able to monitor and control multiple IoT devices and combine contexts and user preferences in order to efficiently optimize the consumption of loads.

VOLTTRON [21] was developed by the Pacific Northwest National Laboratory (PNNL) [22]. VOLTTRON is an agent-based platform developed in Python 2.7 and can be used on single-board computers. VOLTTRON allows the implementation of EMS in the end-user-side using connection drivers that enable the integration of loads, resources, and IoT devices that use building automation and control networks (BACnet), distributed network protocol (DNP3), Modbus/RTU, Modbus/TCP, Obix RESTful, Rainforest Emu2 (an energy monitoring unit), and smart energy profile 2.0 (SEP2, IEEE 2030.5). In a network of VOLTTRON nodes, the platform uses a distributed approach where no centralized node is needed. Centralized agents are used for service deployments, such as weather forecasting and monitor services.

Resilient Information Architecture Platform for Smart Grid (RIAPS) was created by LF Energy [23], it is a software platform for real-time applications that targets buildings and microgrids [24]. The distributed platform uses nodes that can join and leave groups at any time. Within the RIAPS platform, there are two types of nodes that can be used: control and destination nodes. The integration of loads, resources, and IoT devices in RIAPS is done with RIAPS_device that enables the use of several protocols, such as RS-232, RS-485, TCP/IP (ethernet), inter-integrated circuit (I2C), common general-purpose input/output (GPIO) pins, Modbus, DNP3, and IEEE 61850.

In Boussada et al. [25], it is proposed IoT-based privacy-preserving aware data transmission for e-health. This solution addresses the requirements of privacy data. It ensures the privacy of the content by encrypting the data exchanged using symmetric keys, which are in turn encrypted according to the proposed lightweight identity-based encryption (L-IBE) scheme. It also meets all contextual privacy requirements.

Yi-ning liu et al. [26] proposes a privacy-preserving raw data collection without a trusted authority for IoT, in which the participant's data is collected and obscured with the data of another individual in a group in order to mask the participant's privacy. Individual data is kept in raw, while the source of the collection is hidden from outside users. No trusted authority is required, which is more appropriate for

real-world applications. It guarantees the usefulness of all the data and the privacy of the data at the same time.

Quanyu Zhao et al. [27] proposes a blockchain-based privacy-preserving remote data integrity checking scheme for IoT information systems, this system leverages the Lifted EC-ElGamal cryptosystem (The Lifted EC-ElGamal cryptosystem is an asymmetric key cryptography algorithm for public-key cryptography that is based on the exchange of Diffie - Hellman keys. It consists of three components, including key generation, encryption, and decryption), bilinear pairing, and blockchain to support efficient verification of public batch signatures and protect security and IoT system data privacy. This solution is able to provide correctness, privacy, dynamics, public verification, and security.

III. ENERGY MANAGEMENT SOLUTION SUPPORTED BY IOT

The IoT concept has been revolutionizing the world of energy. By being able to collect energy data, IoT devices can be key elements of energy management systems. Seizing this opportunity, the authors proposed an EMS supported by IoT devices where data privacy and security are addressed, allowing multiple accesses and replying accordingly to the user's permission.

A. Proposed Architecture

The proposed software architecture was designed to allow the implementation of an EMS centred on user privacy that is supported by IoT. This research proposes a framework that allows, through IoT devices, the collection and monitoring of energy consumption data, and the maintenance of data privacy. The proposed solution protects the data by replying to HTTP data requests according to the permission of the requester.

The proposed solution, as seen in Figure 1, is composed of the following components: IoT integration (consisting of the integration drivers for sensors, actuators, and EnAPlugs [28]), middleware (storage, EMS models, and API), and presentation (tools for data visualization and interpretation that can be applied to different platforms).

The IoT integration component allows the collection and monitoring of energy loads and resources in a building. However, there is a problem with the integration of heterogeneous IoT devices because they use multiple communication technologies with multiple protocols, not promoting the interoperability and cooperation needed to deploy EMS in buildings. The proposed solution addresses this issue by implemented multiple connection drivers where IoT devices can be connected. For IoT devices that use proprietary protocols, the API of Home Assistant is used. This open-source solution enables the integration of IoT devices while providing an HTTP API, that is integrated into the proposed solution.

Figure 1. Proposed Architecture

The middleware aims to transfer the data from the IoT devices to a database where all the data is stored. The middleware is also responsible for the integration and execution of EMS models, such as energy forecasting, load management, and transactive energy participation. The REST API is implemented in middleware, but the replies are processed in the presentation component to enable the filtering of data according to permissions and privacy.

The data presentation component fetches the data from the middleware, processes, and analyses it, taking into account the data privacy using JavaScript object notation web tokens (JWT) to protect the platform user so that no one else has access to data that does not have permission to access. The JWT are generated in the middleware and by request from the user. For the generation of a JWT, the user must provide the entity that will have the token, the expiration date, data sources available (e.g., total consumption), and data permission level (e.g., aggregated by hour periods, or real-time).

The system is implemented in Python 3.9, which was chosen because of its ability to receive data mining and learning models while providing a stable programming structure to provide a RESTful API.

B. IoT integration

This solution integrated sensors and actuators. The sensors make it possible to collect data in almost all situations and are used in several fields, one of which is the energy sector. The sensors can also be used to collect contextual data, such as temperature, humidity, and movement.

Actuators, operating in the opposite direction to a sensor, allowing the control of the physical resource, turning an electrical input into physical action. The combination among sensors and actuators is common in IoT, providing more contextual information regarding a resource, e.g., smart plugs with energy monitoring of EnAPlugs that monitor the surrounding of the resource.

The proposed solution uses the concept of drivers not only to integrate IoT devices but also to allow an abstraction layer between IoT devices and the middleware. IoT devices are modelled by their sensor and actuation abilities, that they can have or not. Therefore, independent of the protocol, an IoT device is modelled using the same model, enabling the manipulation of multiple data sources without the need of rewriting code. This also enables the future integration of new drivers without the need of updating the code upstream. The configuration of IoT devices also defines the reading periodicity (if applied) – MQTT and AMQP protocols do not need read periods because the data flows from the broker to clients.

C. Data access tool based on JWT tokens

The data access tool is based on JSON Web Tokens (JWT) that are used to control the access to data and thus, promoting and maintaining user privacy. JWT is an open standard (RFC 7519) that defines a compact and independent way to transmit information safely between parties. This information can be verified and trusted because it is signed. JSON Web Tokens are signed by a secret key with the hash-based message authentication code (HMAC) algorithm. Although JWT can be encrypted to provide confidentiality, the proposed solution is, currently, focused on signed tokens. Signed tokens can verify the integrity of statements contained in them, while encrypted tokens hide those statements. Having the tokens signed we managed to ensure that only the person with the secret key was the one who signed it.

JWT can be used for authorization which is the most common scenario for their use. After the user is logged in, each request will include a JWT, allowing the user to access routes, services, and resources that are made available by the token. JWT can also be used for information exchange, they are a good solution to transmit information securely, because as they can be signed, we are sure that the senders are whom they say they are, in addition to how the signature is calculated using the header and the payload, you can also check if the information has been tampered with.

The structure of a JWT consists of three parts separated by points, which are: header, payload, and signature. The header consists of two parts, the type of the token and the signing algorithm used. The payload contains the claims, which are data (almost any JSON data) that the developer includes into the JWT. Finally, the signature, to create the signature, you have to have the encoded header, the encoded payload, the secret key, and the algorithm specified in the header.

JWT was chosen because it has several benefits over other technologies. JSON is less verbose than extension markup language (XML), when coded its size is also smaller, making JWT more compact than security assertion markup language (SAML). This makes JWT a good choice to be transmitted in HTTP environments.

D. Application programming interface (API)

The proposed solution implements a REST API, in which users can request data access using the JWT. The replies are provided according to the JWT. For example, the same route, can provide the real-time energy consumption of the air conditioning or the energy consumption of the last hour.

The routes implemented are described in Table 1. For each route, the JWT can/must be sent as the reply will depend on the user permissions. Because, currently, only routes for requesting data are implemented, the HTTP method is GET to all Table 1 routes.

Table 1. Routes available in the provided REST API

Route	Body
/building/energy	None
/building/energy/history	JSON with query dates
/device/[id]/energy	None
/device/[id]/status	None
/device/[id]/history	JSON with query dates

In order to reply to requests, the proposed solution starts by validating the JWT and verify the access permission that the user has over a giver device and building. The permissions are (i) set over devices and data type (e.g., the JWT is only valid for the /building/energy request), and (ii) set over, one or more, data presentation types: real-time, aggregated by periods (i.e., 15 minutes, 1 hour, and 1 day), embargo period (i.e., 15 minutes, 1 hour, 1 day, and 1 month). By allowing the user to define the data permission for each entity, that he gives access to data, it is possible to give the control to the user and avoid the sharing of data go beyond the needs of the external entity. Therefore, the proposed solution complied with the GDPR [11] by empowering the user to allow full control of his/her data.

IV. CASE STUDY

The proposed solution was tested and validated with real data (regarding an office building). The case study defined

considers a co-working building where spaces are sub-rented to several users. In which we have three types of entities: the owner of the building, the user of the building, and the microgrid operator. This case study will analyse the potential of the system for its ability to maintain the privacy of its users' data. In this way, the user of an office can only access the aggregated consumption data (15 minutes aggregation) of only the room where he/she rents, the manager of the microgrid can access aggregated data of the building (15 minutes aggregation), and the owner of the building can access the data of the building in real-time.

The platform was assembled in a building that already had a supervisory control and data acquisition (SCADA) system with several energy analysers. Each office has IoT devices, connected to the SCADA system and integrated into the proposed solution using HTTP, which monitors the energy consumption. The generation of JWT is the responsibility of the building's manager that will generate a unique JWT for the other two entities (i.e., users that rent a workplace, and the microgrid operator).

The generation of the token for the user who is going to rent the office is done at the time of the lease and will have the same duration as the duration of the lease contract, as soon as it ends, the user no longer has access to the data of that office and thus the token expires.

As mentioned before, the building owner has access to the building data in real-time while the other has access to aggregated data, using 15 minutes of aggregation. Regarding the '/building/energy' route, which provides the consumption data, the building manager can access detailed consumption by device, the user that rented a workplace has access to detailed consumption regarding its devices, and the microgrid operator only has access to the building's total consumption. The route only returns the last values measured, according to the permission of the JWT (e.g., the building manager receives the real-time data, and the two other entities receive the data of the previous 15 minutes – as a unique value).

Figures 2-4 show the results of routines made to monitor the building with the results of each entity. The monitoring period was from 9 a.m. to 6 p.m.

Figure 2. Energy data read by the building owner

Figure 3. Energy data read by the microgrid manager

Figure 4. Energy data read by the office user

The graph of building owner, Figure 2, shows the detail consumption of the buildings, where 10-seconds readings are provided for individual energy measurements, including several rooms and HVAC units. The graph of Figure 3 shows the reading data made available to the microgrid manager, which represents the consumption of the entire building using 15 minutes measuring readings. Figure 4 shows the results made available to the user that rented an office, which has access to individual energy measurements in 15 minutes periods. Throughout the data, we can see that we have some peaks created by the consumption of HVAC_1 and HVAC_2 units, which make the total consumption to be higher between 13:45 and 16:00.

The graphs of Figures 2, 3, and 4 were created using the same route (/building/energy) but with different JWT, corresponding to the three entities involved in this case study. This way, it is possible to guarantee data security, both for users who rent an office and the building.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, it was proposed an integration platform for internet of things (IoT) devices with data preservation using JavaScript object notation web tokens (JWT). The proposed solution prevents data leakage caused by unreliable third

parties. With increasing data demands, our platform guarantees an all-data utility and individual data privacy at the same time. This not only increases the value of the data but also eliminates concerns about privacy leakage.

The proposed solution was tested with a case study using real data that represented an office building where several entities can access the data. The results showed that by using JWT, the systems can share data while respecting the users' rights and wills, passing the decision to the user (the owner of the data). This is an important asked in smart grids where energy-related data flow without addressing privacy issues.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work has received funding from the EU Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under project TradeRES (grant agreement No 864276). The work has been done also in the scope of project UIDB/00760/2020, financed by FEDER Funds through COMPETE program and from National Funds through (FCT).

REFERENCES

- [1] B. Zhou, W. Li, K. W. Chan, Y. Cao, Y. Kuang, X. Liu, and X. Wang, "Smart home energy management systems: Concept, configurations, and scheduling strategies," in *Renewable and Sustainable Energy*

- Reviews, vol. 61, Elsevier Ltd, 2016, pp. 30–40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2016.03.047>
- [2] Z. Vale, H. Morais, P. Faria, and C. Ramos, "Distribution system operation supported by contextual energy resource management based on intelligent SCADA," in *Renewable Energy*, vol. 52, 2013, pp. 143–153. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2012.10.019>
 - [3] L. Yu, W. Xie, D. Xie, Y. Zou, D. Zhang, Z. Sun, L. Zhang, Y. Zhang, and T. Jiang, "Deep Reinforcement Learning for Smart Home Energy Management," in *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 7, no. 4, April 2020, pp. 2751–2762. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JIOT.2019.2957289>
 - [4] M. A. F. Ghazvini, J. Soares, O. Abrishambaf, R. Castro and Z. Vale, "Demand response implementation in smart households," in *Energy and Buildings*, vol. 143, 2017, pp. 129–148. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2017.03.020>
 - [5] W. Tushar, C. Yuen, T. K. Saha, T. Morstyn, A. C. Chapman, M. J. E. Alam, S. Hanif, and H. V. Poor, "Peer-to-peer energy systems for connected communities: A review of recent advances and emerging challenges," in *Applied Energy*, vol. 282, part. A, 2021, pp. 116–131. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2020.116131>
 - [6] T. Malche, and P. Maheshwary, "Internet of Things (IoT) for building smart home system," in 2017 International Conference on I-SMAC (IoT in Social, Mobile, Analytics and Cloud) (I-SMAC), 2017, pp. 65–70. <https://doi.org/10.1109/I-SMAC.2017.8058258>
 - [7] E. Orsi, and S. Nesmachnow, "Smart home energy planning using IoT and the cloud," in 2017 IEEE URUCON, 2017, pp. 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.1109/URUCON.2017.8171843>
 - [8] T. Petrović, and H. Morikawa, "Active sensing approach to electrical load classification by smart plug," in 2017 IEEE Power & Energy Society Innovative Smart Grid Technologies Conference (ISGT), 2017, pp. 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISGT.2017.8086053>
 - [9] M. Alaa, A. A. Zaidan, B. B. Zaidan, M. Talal, and M. L. M. Kiah, "A review of smart home applications based on Internet of Things," in *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, vol. 97, 2017, pp. 48–65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnca.2017.08.017>
 - [10] D. Geneiatakis, I. Kounelis, R. Neisse, I. Nai-Fovino, G. Steri, and G. Baldini, "Security and privacy issues for an IoT based smart home," in 2017 40th International Convention on Information and Communication Technology, Electronics and Microelectronics (MIPRO), 2017, pp. 1292–1297. <https://doi.org/10.23919/MIPRO.2017.7973622>
 - [11] The European Parliament And The Council Of The European Union, "Regulation (EU) 2016/679 Of The European Parliament And Of The Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation)," in *Official Journal of the European Union*, vol. L 119, April 2016, pp. 1–88.
 - [12] J. Teicher, "The little-known story of the first IoT device," in IBM, 2018.
 - [13] I. Lee, "The Internet of Things for enterprises: An ecosystem, architecture, and IoT service business model," in *Internet of Things*, vol. 7, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iot.2019.100078>
 - [14] Statista, "Smart Home Report 2018—Control and Connectivity," in Statista: Hamburg, Germany, 2018.
 - [15] S. Heo, W. Park, and I. Lee, "Energy management based on communication of smart plugs and inverter for smart home systems," in 2017 International Conference on Information and Communication Technology Convergence (ICTC), 2017, pp. 810–812. doi: 10.1109/ICTC.2017.8190788
 - [16] L. Barbierato, A. Estebsari, E. Pons, M. Pau, F. Salassa, M. Ghirardi, and E. Patti, "A Distributed IoT Infrastructure to Test and Deploy Real-Time Demand Response in Smart Grids," in *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 6, no. 1, February 2019, pp. 1136–1146. doi: 10.1109/JIOT.2018.2867511
 - [17] F. Terroso-Saenz, A. González-Vidal, A. P. Ramallo-González, and A. F. Skarmeta, "An open IoT platform for the management and analysis of energy data," in *Future Generation Computer Systems*, vol. 92, 2019, pp. 1066–1079. doi: 10.1016/j.future.2017.08.046
 - [18] L. Gomes, Z. Vale, and J. M. Corchado, "Microgrid management system based on a multi-agent approach: An office building pilot," in *Measurement: Journal of the International Measurement Confederation*, vol. 154, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measurement.2019.107427>
 - [19] L. Gomes, J. Spinola, Z. Vale, and J. M. Corchado, "Agent-based architecture for demand side management using real-time resources' priorities and a deterministic optimization algorithm," in *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 241, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.118154>
 - [20] L. Gomes, Z. A. Vale, and J. M. Corchado, "Multi-Agent Microgrid Management System for Single-Board Computers: A Case Study on Peer-to-Peer Energy Trading," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, 2020, pp. 64169–64183. doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2985254
 - [21] VOLTTRON, "VOLTTRON™ documentation!", (accessed on 30/04/2021) <https://volttron.readthedocs.io/en/develop/index.html>
 - [22] B. Akyol, C. H. Allwardt, Z. W. Beech, J. B. Chapman, J. N. Haack, S. Katipamula, R. G. Lutes, and K. E. Monson, "VOLTTRON™ 2016," June 2016, PNNL-25499 (accessed on 30/04/2021) https://volttron.org/sites/default/files/publications/PNNL_25499_VOLTTRON_2016.pdf
 - [23] The Linux Foundation, The Linux Foundation Launches LF ENERGY, New Open Source Coalition, 12 July 2018.
 - [24] S. Eisele, I. Mardari, A. Dubey, and G. Karsai, "RIAPS: Resilient Information Architecture Platform for Decentralized Smart Systems," in 2017 IEEE 20th International Symposium on Real-Time Distributed Computing (ISORC), 2017, pp. 125–132. doi: 10.1109/ISORC.2017.22
 - [25] R. Boussada, B. Hamdane, M. E. Elhdhili, and L. A. Saidane, "Privacy-preserving aware data transmission for IoT-based e-health," in *Computer Networks*, vol. 162, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comnet.2019.106866>
 - [26] Y. Liu, Y. Wang, X. Wang, Z. Xia, and Jing-Fang Xu, "Privacy-preserving raw data collection without a trusted authority for IoT," in *Computer Networks*, vol. 148, 2019, pp. 340–348. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comnet.2018.11.028>
 - [27] Q. Zhao, S. Chen, Z. Liu, T. Baker, and Y. Zhang, "Blockchain-based privacy-preserving remote data integrity checking scheme for IoT information systems," in *Information Processing & Management*, vol. 57, issue 6, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ipm.2020.102355>
 - [28] L. Gomes, F. Sousa, and Z. Vale, "An Intelligent Smart Plug with Shared Knowledge Capabilities," in *Sensors*, vol. 18, no. 11, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s181113961>